

Sorption and Desorption of Cobalt by Soils and Soil Components

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The sorption desorption of cobalt was studied on different soils of India and different components of soil at cobalt concentrations within the range $0.5 - 8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ with $0.01M$ CaCl_2 as background electrolyte at pH 6.5. The maximum adsorption of Co occurs at pH 6.5 and almost complete sorption occurs within 48 h. The sorption was maximum with ferromanganese oxide followed by organic materials. The order of desorption was clay minerals > humic acids > ferro manganese oxide.

The sorption isotherms for natural soils at low site coverages were linear and sorption on different soils was studied. The studies also showed that cobalt sorption in natural soil is largely controlled by ferro-manganese oxide.

Adsorption of ions on natural materials and the ion-exchange properties of clay minerals have been a subject of interest for years. Cobalt, a micronutrient, is adsorbed by clay minerals¹, soils², organic matters³ and Fe and Mn oxides^{4,5}. The objective of the present study was to get information on the relative importance of different soil constituents in controlling retention and movement of cobalt in soil.

Results and Discussion

The experiment of sorption of cobalt on black soil, montmorillonite, humic acid and soil oxide showed that the bulk of cobalt was sorbed rapidly within 2-3 h and further sorption on montmorillonite and soil oxide occurred slowly for several more hours. So, an equilibrium time of 48 h was chosen for experiments since by this time equilibrium cobalt sorption was virtually complete.

Fig. 1 shows that sorption of cobalt increases with increased pH upto 6.5 for all the adsorbents

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on sorption of cobalt by (●) soil oxide - $8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (△) humic acid - $4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (▲) montmorillonite - $3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and (○) black soil - $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

and then decreased. For montmorillonite, the rate of increase in sorption is the greatest over the pH range 4.3-6.5, suggesting that cobalt is adsorbed on montmorillonites by two types of mechanism, one being cation-exchange behaviour while the other corresponding to negative charges at edges and broken bonds⁶⁻⁸. The change in adsorption with pH on clay surface and soil oxide may also be due to changes in prevalent forms of cobalt species, and for humic and fulvic acids this may be due to increase in degree of ionisation and complex formation with cobalt ions.

Fig. 2 shows that substantial amounts of cobalt were sorbed by black soil, montmorillonite, humic acids and soil oxide in presence of large excess of calcium ions. At higher calcium concentration the sorption of cobalt is reduced which may be due

Fig. 2. Effect of calcium chloride concentration on the sorption of cobalt by (●) soil oxide - $8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (△) humic acid - $4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (▲) montmorillonite - $3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and (○) black soil - $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

to decrease in activity of Co^{II} ions by increasing solution ionic strength^{6,9} or due to competition from Ca^{II} for sorption sites¹⁰.

The adsorption studies on black soil and different soil components (Fig. 3) shows that at the studied concentrations of cobalt solution the sorption is in the order: soil oxide > humic acid > fulvic acid > clay minerals (montmorillonite, > illite > kaolinite > soil. The sorption isotherms are almost linear for soil oxide, humic acid, fulvic acid and soil and L-type for clay minerals. More sorption on soil oxide than on clay minerals may be due to the amorphous nature of soil oxide as poorly crystalline minerals with their relative disorder are likely to have a greater specific surface area and more charged sites, and are highly reactive. At such reactive sites specific adsorption can take place¹¹. This is supported by the surface area data. The surface area calculated for soil oxide was found to be $806 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ which is higher than that of montmorillonite clay ($680 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Although fulvic acids possess greater number of functional groups than humic acids, the sorption was equal to that on humic acid which may probably be due to the formation of fulvic acids—cobalt complexes¹².

Fig. 3. Cobalt sorption isotherms for (●) soil oxide - $8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (O) fulvic acids - $4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (▲) montmorillonite - $3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (△) illite - $2 \mu\text{g ml}$, (⊙) kaolinite - $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and (■) black soil - $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

The desorption studies (Table 1) show that a substantial amount of cobalt could be desorbed from humic acid, montmorillonite, soil oxide and soil. The percent cobalt desorbed following the order: montmorillonite > humic acid > natural soil > soil oxide. This indicates that minimum

desorption occurs with soil oxide, thereby suggesting more retention capacity of soil oxide and specific adsorption of cobalt on soil oxide. Similar results were reported by Padmanabham⁶.

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF COBALT DESORBED FROM SOIL AND SOIL COMPONENTS

Component	Total amount adsorbed $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	Amount desorbed $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	Desorbed %
Soil	24	14	58
Montmorillonite	264	206	78
Humic acid	376	252	67
Soil oxide	742	275	37

The sorption studies on natural soils (Fig. 4) show that the sorption isotherms in the range of cobalt concentrations studied are linear. These sorption isotherms represent cobalt adsorption at a very low percentage occupation of sorption sites, such as when small amounts of cobalt are added to the soils. The sorption on soils follows the order: $8 > 4 > 5 > 7 > 6 > 2 > 3 > 1$, indicating that sorption of cobalt on soil depends on soil pH ($r = -0.183$), surface area ($r = 0.923$), organic matter ($r = 0.945$), percentage of clay minerals ($r = 0.887$) and cation-exchange capacity of soil¹³ ($r = 0.584$). These data are significant at the 0.001 probability level.

Fig. 4. Cobalt sorption isotherms for whole soils: (●) black soil (8) - $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, (△) alluvial soil (4) - $0.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and (O) red soil (1) - $0.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

These observations support the suggestion that the cobalt sorption by soils is controlled to a large extent by their oxide contentions.

Experimental

The sorption and desorption studies were made with clays, ferromanganese oxides, humic acids, fulvic acids and natural soils.

Eight surface soil samples (0–20 cm) from different parts of India with the following characteristics were used: pH, 6.0–9.2; clay content, 9.0–44.8%; surface area, 21.2–80.6 m² g⁻¹; CEC, 6.5–31.5 meq 100 g, 100 mesh sieved samples were used. Physicochemical properties (Table 2) were determined by the method of Jones *et al.*¹⁴. Calcium saturated samples of alkali bentonite (montmorillonite) from Rajasthan, illite from Morris (Illinois) and kaolinite from Bath (South Carolina) were used for these studies. Ferromanganese concentrations (100 mesh) with 14.1% Fe and 5.5% Mn (acid-oxalate extractable) were used. The X-ray diffraction of the soil oxide revealed no well developed crystallinity. Humic and fulvic acids were prepared from a sample of well-humified basin peat by extraction with 0.5 M NaOH and purified¹⁵. The Ca-forms were used for studies.

cobalt solution (25 ml) (with CaCl₂ concentration ranging from 0.001 to 1.0 M) at pH 6.5±0.1 as discussed earlier. For sorption experiments the adsorbent (250 mg) was treated with 0.5–8 µg ml⁻¹ cobalt solution (0–25 ml) (0.01 M CaCl₂ used as background electrolyte) for 48 h at pH 6.5±0.1. The suspension was centrifuged and cobalt in the supernatant was estimated as discussed earlier. Sorption on different soil samples was effected by equilibrating each soil sample (1 g) with 0.5–1.0 µg ml⁻¹ cobalt solution (0–25 ml) as discussed earlier.

For desorption studies cobalt-sorbed samples (250 mg) of black soil, montmorillonite, humic acid and soil oxide (prepared by treating adsorbent with 25 ml of cobalt solution as discussed in sorption experiment) were shaken with 0.01M CaCl₂ (25 ml) for 48 h. The suspensions were centrifuged and cobalt was estimated as above. All the samples were analysed in duplicate.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SOILS

Sample no.	Place	Taxonomical name	Silt %	Clay %	pH (1 : 2.5)	Organic C %	CaCO ₃ %	Free Fe ₂ O ₃ %	CEC meq/100 g	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹
1.	Bangalore	Red typic haplustalf	48.1	18.3	6.0	0.44	0.6	10.2	6.5	21.2
2.	Datawali	Aridisol sub-grp. typic orthids	37.5	9.0	7.2	0.40	5.2	3.6	10.0	24.3
3.	Sikandra Rao	Acidisol sub-grp. typic arigids	52.5	4.0	9.2	0.35	8.2	6.8	10.4	36.6
4.	Hathras	Alluvial typic ustochrept	38.8	13.1	7.9	0.56	8.0	3.6	11.6	30.6
5.	Bank of Yamuna Tappal	Calciorthents	27.1	8.5	8.1	0.54	9.0	6.7	8.0	26.4
6.	Atrauli	Calciorthents	22.6	4.4	8.5	0.44	10.8	5.4	9.4	34.8
7.	Khair	Aridisol sub-grp. typic orthids	44.9	15.2	7.5	0.50	6.6	5.6	9.6	27.2
8.	Indore	Fine clayey mixed hyperthermic, typic argiustoll	47.0	44.8	7.0	0.88	2.5	1.4	31.5	80.6
	Soil oxide								286.2	806
	Humic acid								193.6	324

The effect of time on sorption was studied by equilibrating the adsorbents (black soil, montmorillonite, humic acid and ferro-manganese oxide) (250 mg) with cobalt solution (25 ml; concentration 1.0 to 8 µg ml⁻¹) containing 0.01 M CaCl₂ as a background electrolyte. The samples were continuously shaken for various time periods (0.5–96 h) followed by centrifugation. Cobalt was determined in supernatant using the reported method¹⁶. The amounts of cobalt sorbed after various time intervals were calculated by depletion.

The effect of equilibrium pH on cobalt sorption was investigated at pH values ranging from 2 to 10 (adjusted by 0.1 M HCl or Ca(OH)₂) by treating the adsorbents (250 mg) with cobalt solution (25 ml) as discussed earlier. To study the effect of background CaCl₂ concentration on cobalt sorption, the adsorbent (250 mg) was treated with

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